

Original Research

Correlation Between Physicochemical Parameters and Heavy Metal Levels in Lake Victoria, Kenya - Ecological Relevance to Nile Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*)

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ABSTRACT

Lake Victoria is increasingly threatened by anthropogenic pollution, with implications for water quality, fisheries, and public health. This study examined the relationship between physicochemical parameters and heavy metal concentrations [lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd), zinc (Zn), copper (Cu), iron (Fe), chromium (Cr)] in Lake Victoria. During the dry season, water samples were collected from six sites in Siaya County, and physicochemical parameters were measured *in situ*. Heavy metals were analyzed using atomic absorption spectrophotometry, and data were subjected to Kruskal–Wallis tests, Dunn’s post hoc analysis, and Spearman’s rank correlations in R. Results revealed that most physicochemical parameters were within WHO limits, although conductivity and salinity varied significantly ($p < 0.05$) across sites. Fe was significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher in Kokach and Wichlum, while Cr levels were lowest ($p < 0.05$) in Kokach. Positive correlation between Fe and both temperature ($r = 0.77$) and dissolved solids ($r = 0.77$) was observed, while Cd was negatively correlated with conductivity ($r = -0.97$). Other associations were weak and not statistically significant. In conclusion, there is a strong association between physicochemical parameters and heavy metal concentrations in Lake Victoria, indicating that monitoring these selected physicochemical variables can serve for predicting heavy metal dynamics. Regular monitoring and integrated catchment management are therefore recommended to safeguard the lake’s ecological integrity. Further studies incorporating seasonal variation are necessary.

KEYWORDS: Ecology, Heavy Metals, Lake Victoria, Nile Tilapia, Physicochemical parameters.

INTRODUCTION

The Lake Victoria ecosystem is under threat from pollution originating from anthropogenic activities such as industrial effluents, agricultural runoff, urbanization, and population growth within its catchment (Juma et al., 2014). These pressures contribute to nutrient loading and heavy metal (HMs) contamination, which threaten aquatic life, fisheries, and public health (Muthoka et al., 2024).

Heavy metals such as cadmium (Cd), lead (Pb), mercury (Hg), chromium (Cr), and nickel (Ni) are of major concern because they are toxic, persistent, and bioaccumulate (Argun, 2025). Heavy metals cannot be degraded and tend to accumulate in sediments and aquatic organisms (Rajendra Singh et al., 2017). Sediments act as both sinks and secondary sources of

metals, releasing them into the water under changing environmental conditions (Hacisalihoğlu and Karaer, 2016). Consequently, the interplay between water chemistry and sediments strongly influences heavy metal distribution and ecological impacts (Miranda et al., 2021).

Physicochemical parameters such as pH, dissolved oxygen (DO), electrical conductivity (EC), temperature, total nitrogen (TN), and total phosphorus (TP) regulate the solubility, mobility, and bioavailability of metals in aquatic systems (Hacisalihoğlu and Karaer, 2016). For instance, low pH increases metal solubility, while organic matter and suspended solids enhance metal binding in sediments.

These dynamics determine contamination patterns and affect the physiological health of aquatic organisms (Muthoka et al., 2024).

Nile tilapia is especially vulnerable to heavy metal exposure. Accumulation of metals in its tissues can impair growth, reproduction, and organ function, and in turn reduce fishery productivity (Shalan, 2024). Tilapia, being the most consumed fish in Kenya, and elevated heavy metal levels may pose food safety risks for human and animal populations (Outa et al., 2020). Although studies have reported the presence of heavy metals in Lake Victoria's water, sediments, and fish (Ogoyi et al., 2011), few have examined how physicochemical parameters regulate these contaminants and their physiological implications for fish in the Kenyan part of the lake (Kundu et al., 2017). This study, therefore, investigated the association between physicochemical parameters and heavy metal levels in Lake Victoria, Kenya, which could have detrimental effects on Nile tilapia's physiology.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area

The study was carried out at six landing beaches along Lake Victoria in Siaya County during the dry season (December 2024). Lake Victoria, the second-largest freshwater lake in the world, is located in East Africa, bordered by Kenya, Uganda, and Tanzania (Latitudes 13°00'N and 4°0'E and Longitudes 31°37' and 34°53'E). The Kenyan portion covers approximately 4,100 km², accounting for about 6% of the lake's total surface area. The lake has an average depth of 40 m, with inflows from major rivers such as Yala, Nzoia, Sondu-Miriu, and Kuja, and drains into the Nile through Jinja, Uganda (Yunana et al., 2017). The climate of Siaya County, one of Kenya's counties located along Lake Victoria, is tropical, characterized by bimodal rainfall, which ranges from 1,200 to 1,800 mm annually, and temperatures that average 20–30°C (Yunana et al., 2017). Water samples were collected from six sites along the Siaya County shoreline of Lake Victoria, namely, Usenge (Latitude -0.07427, Longitude 34.06205), Sika (Latitude 0.12824, Longitude 34.02828), Kokach (Latitude -0.1906, Longitude 34.38927), Nyenye Got (Latitude -0.04435, Longitude 34.02531), Wichlum, and Gul (Figure 1).

Water Parameters Determination

Water parameters (temperature, pH, total dissolved solids, electric conductivity, specific gravity, and salinity) were measured *in situ* during sample collection using a multiparameter probe pH meter (SN: 407114, EU/PPE/0000004354). The probe was introduced into the water column up to 4 cm below, allowed to settle, and then stabilized to record the readings.

Water Sample Collection, Transportation, and Storage

Three water samples were collected from each sampling site, using sterile glass water collection

bottles approximately 20 cm deep from the water surface to minimize contamination from surface film, and then transferred into one-liter glass bottles. Water bottles were labeled appropriately according to the sampling site. Two milliliters of concentrated nitric acid were then added immediately to the water samples to dissolve any traces of heavy metals. The samples were placed inside a cooling box during transportation for heavy metals analysis at Egerton University's Njoro Campus, Safe Food Reference Laboratory, where samples were stored at 4°C.

Figure 1: Map of Kenya and Siaya County showing sampling sites within Lake Victoria

Determination of Heavy Metal Levels (Pb, Cd, Cr, Zn, Cu, Fe)

Instruments and Preparation

All the necessary equipment and reagents to be used were assembled in preparation for the analysis. All the flasks were washed thoroughly with soap and tap water to remove contaminants, then rinsed. They were subsequently soaked in a 10% nitric acid solution for 12 hours and rinsed with deionized water. Afterward, they were dried in a hot air oven for 60 minutes at 80°C.

Water Heavy Metals Extraction

Ten milliliters (10 mL) of the water samples were measured and placed into a conical flask; then, five milliliters (5 mL) of 69% v/v nitric acid mixed with 37% v/v hydrochloric acid (1:3) was added. The sample mixture was heated at 95°C in a water bath for

approximately 3 to 4 hours, until its volume was reduced by half to about 5-7 ml. The mixture was cooled, then filtered using Whatman filter paper number 42 into 50 ml conical flasks, and topped up to the mark with deionized water (Ranasinghe et al., 2016). All water samples were digested in triplicate, labelled, and then transferred to bottles for storage, pending heavy metal analysis (iron, copper, zinc, lead, chromium, and cadmium).

Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry (AAS) for Heavy Metals Analysis

The analysis of Fe, Cu, Zn, Pb, Cr, and Cd from the water-digested samples was determined using an atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AA-700 SHIMADZU model). The concentrations were determined using standard curves generated from each standard solution prepared from the stock solutions of the heavy metals. Each sample was run in triplicate to

determine HMs levels, and the averages were used in statistical analysis.

Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer Calibration

To ensure the accuracy of the AAS machine and confirm the results, calibration curves for each heavy metal were established using a standard solution following Perkin-Elmer (1996) guidelines. The working calibration was prepared from a concentrated stock solution of Fe, Cu, Zn, Pb, Cr, and Cd, reducing the original 1000 ppm concentration to the desired lower concentrations of 0.02 ppm to 10 ppm. The solutions and blanks were analyzed in AAS, and calibration curves for each metal were generated, which were used to determine the metal concentrations in water samples. Table 1 shows the AAS working conditions. The minimum detection level for the analyzed metals was 0.001 ppm.

Table 1: Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer operating conditions

Parameters	Pb	Cd	Cr	Cu	Zn	Fe
Wave length	283.2	228.9	357.9	324.7	213.9	248.3
Slit width	1.0	0.5	0.2	1.0	0.5	0.3
Flame type		Air Acetylene	N ₂ O\ acetylene	Air acetylene		Air acetylene
Detection limit (ppm)	0.02	0.0006	0.005	0.03	0.002	0.04
Lamp current (mA)	6	3	5	5.0		8

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using the R programming language, version 4.3.1 (2025). Normality was assessed using the Shapiro-Wilk test at a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ for physicochemical parameters and heavy metals. The violation of normality necessitated the use of the Kruskal-Wallis test for group comparisons and the Dunn post hoc test to differentiate the means. Spearman's rank correlation was used to determine the strength of association between the physicochemical parameters and levels of heavy metals in water. The statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$ for all tests; results are presented as mean \pm standard deviation.

RESULTS

Physicochemical Parameters of Water

Despite spatial variation among the sampling sites, all of the water physicochemical parameters were within the WHO recommendations. Temperature, specific gravity, pH, and total dissolved solids did not differ significantly among sites ($p > 0.05$), although Kokach recorded the highest temperature ($31.35 \pm 4.12^\circ\text{C}$) and the lowest pH (6.22). Dissolved solids and salinity showed statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) differences among sites. Kokach had the highest dissolved solids (105.00 ± 14.70 mg/L), while Nyenye Got presented the highest salinity (1.00 ± 0.00 ppt) (Table 2).

Table 2: Physicochemical parameters of water across sampling sites

SITE	Temperature (°C)	Dissolved solids (mg/L)	Conductivity (µS/cm)	Specific Gravity (mg/L)	pH	Salinity (ppt)
Usenge	26.87 ± 0.03	50.67 ± 0.67^a	65 ± 17.95	1.07 ± 0.03	7.63 ± 0.05	0 ± 00^a
Sika	25.53 ± 0.20	48.33 ± 0.33^a	107.33 ± 58.85	1 ± 00	7.91 ± 0.05	0 ± 00^a
Kokach	31.35 ± 4.12	105 ± 14.7^b	11.23 ± 0.49	1 ± 00	6.22 ± 0.01	0.01 ± 00^a
Nyenye Got	26.93 ± 0.55	50.33 ± 0.33^a	107.33 ± 38.18	1.07 ± 0.03	7.61 ± 0.01	1 ± 00^b
Wichitum	27.41 ± 0.59	55.76 ± 0.17^a	107.33 ± 38.18	1.00	6.96 ± 0.04	0 ± 00^a
Gul	26.54 ± 0.20	51.32 ± 0.72^a	65.00 ± 17.95	1.08	7.29 ± 0.03	0 ± 00^a
p-value	0.103	0.035	0.417	0.190	0.075	0.019
Normal (WHO,2004)	25-30 (°C)	0-500 (mg/L)	100-2,000 (µS/cm)	1.0000-1.0020	6.5-8.5	<2ppt

a, b: values bearing different superscript letters in the same column are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

Water Heavy Metal Concentration Across Sites

Iron and chromium had significant ($p < 0.05$) differences across sites (Table 3). Fe levels were significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher in Kokach and Wichlum, while Cr levels were lowest ($p < 0.05$) in Kokach. The other heavy metals (Pb, Cd, Zn, or Cu) were not

statistically significant across sites ($p > 0.05$). However, zinc was below the machine detection limit (0.005 mg/L), and Fe values presented as 0 ± 0 mg/kg were also below the machine detection limit (0.01 mg/L).

Table 3: Concentrations of heavy metals (mg/L) across sites

Site	Pb	Cd	Zn	Cu	Fe	Cr
Gul	0.337±0.0	0.190±0.001	0±0	3.51±0.014	0±0 ^a	5.43±0.014 ^b
Kokach	0.036±0.0	0.285±0.001	0±0	2.24±0.028	8.84±0.042 ^b	0.09±0.028 ^a
Lwanda	0.940±0.0	0.190±0.000	0±0	3.35±0.057	1.15±0.028 ^a	3.87±0.042 ^b
Nyenye Got	0.337±0.0	0.143±0.001	0±0	2.07±0.028	0±0 ^a	5.84±0.057 ^b
Sika	0.337±0.0	0.142±0.001	0±0	2.20±0.141	0±0 ^a	4.06±0.014 ^b
Usenge	0.337±0.0	0.190±0.001	0±0	3.99±0.028	0±0 ^a	5.03±0.042 ^b
Wichlum	0.664±0.0	0.142±0.001	0±0	3.02±0.007	5.76±0.028 ^b	1.98±0.057 ^b
P. Value	0.0880	0.0745	-	0.0504	0.0447	0.0463
WHO	0.01	0.01	0.5	2	10	0.05

a, b: values bearing different superscript letters in the same column are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

Correlation Between Heavy Metals and Physicochemical Parameters in Lake Victoria

Both water temperatures and total dissolved solids were positively and significantly correlated with Fe ($r =$

0.77). Conductivity presented a strong and statistically significant negative correlation with Cd ($r = -0.97$). Zn was below the detection limit across sites, so it was not correlated. Other correlations were weak to moderate and not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$) (Table 4).

Table 4: Correlations between physicochemical parameters and heavy metal concentrations in water

Variable	Pb	Cd	Zn	Cu	Fe	Cr
Temperature	-0.17 (p=0.71)	0.23 (p=0.61)	NA	-0.22 (p=0.64)	0.77 (p=0.04)	-0.5 (p=0.25)
pH	0.31 (p=0.50)	-0.35 (p=0.44)	NA	0.04 (p=0.94)	-0.67 (p=0.10)	0.4 (p=0.38)
Conductivity	0.44 (p=0.31)	-0.97 (p=0.00)	NA	-0.49 (p=0.27)	-0.32 (p=0.48)	0.26 (p=0.57)
Dissolved. solids	-0.17 (p=0.72)	0.58 (p=0.17)	NA	0.32 (p=0.49)	0.77 (p=0.04)	-0.61 (p=0.14)
Specific. gravity	0.15 (p=0.75)	0.21 (p=0.65)	NA	0.5 (p=0.25)	-0.57 (p=0.18)	0.73 (p=0.06)
Salinity	-0.54 (p=0.21)	0.05 (p=0.92)	NA	-0.67 (p=0.10)	0.15 (p=0.75)	0.13 (p=0.76)

Bolded values are statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

DISCUSSION

Water parameters determine its quality to support aquatic life. The measured physicochemical parameters varied across sampling sites, reflecting anthropogenic inputs and natural spatial heterogeneity. They were within the WHO recommendations for optimal tilapia survival, which is one of the main fish species found in this lake. This finding is consistent with Orina et al. (2020), who recorded temperatures of 23.4-29.5°C, pH of 7.08-9.3, conductivity of 69.0-173.0 mS/m, TDS of 60.7-135.0 mg/L, and DO of 2.4-10.3 mg/L. All sites had a mean temperature of 27.43°C, which is ideal and suitable for the thriving of aquatic health and tilapia physiological functions. However, these values were within the minimum optimal growth temperature range

for *Oreochromis niloticus*, as recommended by the FAO (2012), which is 27°C to 36°C. The highest temperature was recorded at Kokach ($31.35 \pm 4.12^\circ\text{C}$) and the lowest at Sika ($25.53 \pm 0.2^\circ\text{C}$).

Temperature had a significant positive correlation with Fe, indicating that an increase in temperature increases the level of Fe. These findings are consistent with Baharim et al. (2011), who reported that warmer conditions strengthen and lengthen thermal stratification, which drives hypolimnetic deoxygenation; under these anoxic conditions iron is reductively released from sediments, raising dissolved Fe in the lake's water.

According to [Piwowarska et al. \(2024\)](#), rising temperatures affect oxygen solubility and redox potential, which may lead to the formation of insoluble metal species and their removal from solution.

The pH values across the sites (6.22–7.91) fell within the range reported by [Kaddumukasa et al. \(2012\)](#) for Lake Victoria (6.6–9.8), indicating suitable conditions for aquatic life. Slightly acidic conditions at Kokach might be enhancing metal solubility and bioavailability, a mechanism also observed in Lake Naivasha ([Keyombe and Waithaka, 2017](#)). The pH range was within the standard parameter for most freshwater fish, which lies between 6.5 and 8.5, allowing biological functions such as metabolism, enzyme activity, and reproductive processes to operate optimally ([Mariu et al., 2023](#)). The pH had a weak, insignificant positive correlation with Cu and Cr. This indicates that an increase in pH may be enhancing the availability of these metals. These findings are consistent with [Argun \(2025\)](#), who reported that Pb and Cr had weaker positive correlations of 0.12 between Cr and pH and 0.06 between Pb and pH in Ermenek Dam Lake (Turquoise Lake).

Electrical conductivity (EC) varied across the sites (11.24–107.33 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) with a mean of 77.2 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, which is lower compared to [Sitoki et al.'s \(2010\)](#) findings previously reported in Lake Victoria. Kokach showed low values (11.24 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) despite having high dissolved solids (105 ± 14.7), possibly due to the presence of non-electrolytic solutes. Although the measured EC values fall within the acceptable range for freshwater fish (30–500 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), which is considered optimal for growth and physiological performance of Nile tilapia (100 - 500 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$). This result highlights the importance of ion availability for tilapia ([Kelany et al., 2024](#)). The findings differed from [Onyari and Wandiga \(1989\)](#), which had a higher conductivity ($>12,500 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), attributed to suspended organic matter and colloids. The lower water conductivity in Lake Victoria falls into a category described by [Sitoki et al. \(2010\)](#) as lakes with a conductivity of less than 600 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$. The electrical conductivity showed a stronger

negative correlation with Cd, while Cu and Fe have a weak, insignificant negative association, reflecting a competitive ionic influence ([Hacisalihoğlu and Karaer, 2016](#)). The positive correlation with Pb and Cr indicates that these heavy metals are found in dissolved forms in water and contribute to the ionic charge distribution ([Argun, 2025](#)).

Salinity obtained in this study falls within the suitable range for Nile tilapia reproduction. Literature indicates that tilapia can spawn in slightly brackish water, while elevated salinity levels ($>8 \text{ ppt}$) can negatively impact reproductive parameters, including gonad development, egg size, and hatching success ([Armas-Rosales, 2006](#)). Salinity was not correlated with heavy metals, suggesting that salt does not affect their levels in the water ([Lores and Pennock, 1998](#)). For Nile tilapia, moderate salinity supports osmoregulation and ion exchange across gills. However, the continued presence of Cd, Cr, and Fe in the dissolved phase suggests that tilapia remain vulnerable to these metals even under favorable ionic conditions. Thus, acceptable salinity levels alone do not guarantee reduced heavy metal-related ecological risks.

Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) showed a significant positive correlation with Fe, whereas correlations with Pb, Cd, Cu, and Cr were insignificant. Higher TDS values correspond to increased ionic strength and greater availability of dissolved ions, which likely enhance the solubility or mobility of Fe under the hydrochemical conditions of the lakes. In contrast, the other metals appear less responsive to TDS variation in our study, indicating that additional controls such as pH, redox, or sediment interactions dominate their distribution ([Hacisalihoğlu and Karaer, 2016](#)). The TDS levels fall within the reported acceptable range for Nile tilapia (200–500 mg/L), which is associated with good osmoregulatory and metabolic performance in tilapia aquaculture ([Idam and Elsheakh, 2022](#)).

CONCLUSION

Our study findings demonstrated that physicochemical conditions influence heavy metal dynamics in Lake

Victoria. While water quality parameters remained within ranges favorable for Nile tilapia, elevated Fe and Cr in some sites may pose a potential ecological threat to their physiological functions. Regular monitoring and catchment management are recommended to safeguard the lake's ecological integrity. There is also a need to conduct a detailed study across all seasons.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

The National Commission for Science, Technology, and Innovation (Kenya) gave its approval to the proposed research under the license number 773648. Ethical clearance was provided by the Egerton University Institutional Scientific and Ethics Review Committee, Approval No. EUISERC/523/2025.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS

Conception of the study: [TOO, JM, EM]; Methodology and Data collection: [TOO, EM]; Data analysis: [TOO]; Writing - original draft preparation: [TOO]; Funding acquisition: [EM]; Supervision: [JM, EM, WJ, CO]

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data used to obtain the findings of this study can be obtained upon reasonable request from the corresponding author.

DECLARATION OF GENERATIVE AI

During the preparation of this work, the author(s) used Grammarly to improve the clarity of sentences. After using this tool/service, the authors cross-checked and

edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

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